

Competency Based Nursing Education; Challenges and Opportunities

Short running Title: Competency Nursing

Authors : 1. Dr Subhashish Das
Professor,
Department of Pathology
Sri Devaraj Urs Medical College
Tamaka, Kolar-563101

2. Dr. Zeanath C J
Professor,
Department of Medical Surgical Nursing
Department Sri Devaraj Urs College of
Nursing, Tamaka, Kolar-563101

Corresponding Author:

1. Dr Subhashish Das(*)
Professor,
Department of Pathology
Sri Devaraj Urs Medical College
Tamaka, Kolar-563101

Word count (Abstract):-

145 Word count (Article):-

1768 No. of Tables:- 06

No. of Figures:- 03

Conflict of Interest; None

Introduction

Traditional mode of nursing and training is undergoing several changes with emphasis on competency based nursing education. We assess various modes of teaching and learning activities along with professional values and attitudes.

Aim

- Adequate training to the nursing graduates towards acquiring learning skills.
- To help the nursing graduates to demonstrate skills in teaching to individuals and groups in clinical and community health settings.

Materials and methods

The quantitative data was associated with the level of nursing competencies whereas, qualitative data explored the concepts of understanding among students, faculty members and preceptors about CBNE programs.

Result

The quantitative and qualitative findings complemented students' academic satisfaction with the teaching by faculty members and preceptors. Finally, the quantitative and qualitative findings were expanded to explain students' academic satisfaction with the programme.

Conclusion

CBNE helps the students towards acquiring skills towards critical thinking competency and problem solving attitude.

Key words

Competency, Nursing education, Quantitative, Qualitative.

Introduction

The conventional manner of teaching and learning that nursing graduates currently get has led to a lack of proficiency in a number of areas, including critical thinking, problem solving, self-management, and group interaction within an organization.^[1] Many educators are ill-prepared for their teaching roles, few hold postgraduate degrees, and many have been exposed to a content-driven curriculum that has been medically framed and primarily developed and delivered by medical personnel. Nursing faculties have little to no experience working with CBC. Although competency-based curriculum, or CBNE, is recognized as the gold standard for modernizing and expanding health professional education and training to enhance population and health outcomes, its use is still far from ideal. Therefore, the goal of the study was to enhance nursing education by using a competency-based curriculum.^[2,3]

Aims and Objectives

In conformity with Indian Nursing Council (INC) regulations CBNE aims to provide adequate training to the nursing graduates towards acquiring learning skills, making independent decisions and protecting the rights of the patients and also participate as an important member in the healthcare delivery system.^[4]

The ultimate objective of CBNE is to help the nursing graduates to demonstrate skills in teaching to individuals and groups in clinical and community health settings.^[5]

Materials and methods

The study has been conducted in our institute to develop essential features of CBNE in order to meet new challenges of nursing education and comply with the objectives on the INC requirements. The study basically uses convergent mixed methods involving simultaneous collection of quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data was associated with the level of nursing competencies whereas, qualitative data explored the concepts of understanding among students, faculty members and preceptors about CBNE programs.^[6,7]

Prior to the conduct of the exercise a) an orientation program was done among the nursing faculties in order to sensitize them and undertake a 'GAP analysis'. During this exercise, the various advantages opportunities challenges and implications of CBNE were discussed and valuable inputs regarding the various aspects of CBNE were elicited in order to make the CBNE program more relevant and effective.^[8]

The various steps involved towards the formulation of CBNE are illustrated in figure 2 (a,b,c)

Steps towards formulation of CBNE

Process of defining PEOs

Figure 1: Process of defining PEOs

Figure 2(a)

Figure 2(b)

Figure 2(c)

Assessment tool;

Sl. No	Type of course	Tool	Frequency
1.	Theory	Quiz	Thrice per semester
		Assignment	Thrice per semester
		Internal exam	Twice per semester
		Semester end exam	Once per semester
		Course end survey	Once per semester
2.	Project Seminar	Rubrics for evaluation of seminar	Once per semester
		Course end survey	Once per semester
3.	Skill Laboratories	Internal exam	Once per semester
		Semester end exam	Once per semester
		Course end survey	Once per semester
4.	Projects	Rubrics for evaluation of Projects (Internal)	Twice per semester
		Viva-voce (Sem-end exam)	Once per semester
		Course end survey	Once per semester

Table 1:

Rubrics - A rubric explains to students the criteria against which their work will be judged with the “scoring rules”. It is used by faculty in assessing the course outcome attainment in projects and seminars during third year and final year.^[9] This tool is designed to evaluate the students’ capability of self-learning, innovativeness and team management and communication skills. It makes a public key criterion that students can use in developing, reviewing, and judging their own work.^[10]

The following tables show the rubrics for assessment of Project work and seminar. Rubric is to be aligned to the COs.

Rubrics for Project Seminar

Grade/ Criteria	Satisfactory	Good	Very Good	Outstanding
Literature Survey & Selection	Moderate literature review and Fair description	Moderate Literature review and Clear description	Good literature review and Good description	Very Good literature review and Very Good description
Presentation	Fair Presentations of the selected topic	Clear Presentations	Good Presentations	Very Good Presentations
Communication	Fair description of The Concept/Techniques	Clear description of the Concept/ Techniques	Good description of the Concept/ Techniques	Very Good description of the Concept/Techniques

Documentation	Fair documentation	Clear documentation	Good documentation	Very Good documentation
Conclusion	Fair conclusion	Clear conclusion	Good conclusion	Very Good conclusion

Table 2:

CO Attainment is calculated using the performance of every student through the Continuous Internal Evaluation (which includes Assignments, Quiz and Internal exams) and the Semester end examinations.

Fig 3: Course Outcome Attainment Process

CO Attainment Levels: Every course will have to set the CO Attainment levels using the threshold. Three attainment levels namely Attainment Level 3, Attainment Level 2 & Attainment Level 1 have been identified as shown below, where 3 is the highest and 1 being lowest. Each level is defined as the % of students scoring more than the threshold.

Rubric for Surveys

Attainment Level 3:	If attainment percentage is $\geq 60\%$
Attainment Level 2:	If attainment percentage is $\geq 50\%$ to $< 60\%$
Attainment Level 1:	If attainment percentage is $\geq 10\%$ to $< 50\%$

Table 3:

Results

Module No.	Core Competencies	Specific competencies	Hours Allotment	
			Theory	Practical
I	Health Care Communication and Interpersonal Skills	C1- Health Care Communication Competency and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. C2- Health Care Communication and psychological defense mechanisms. C3- Health Care Communication and conflict Resolution Process C4- Health Care Communication competencies in special needs C5- Health Care Communication and special techniques	10	20
II	Advanced Nursing Core Competencies	C1 – Professionalism with ethical and legal principles C2 - Core Competencies in Nursing Process C3 - Core Competencies in Critical Nursing Care C4 - Core competencies for Infection Prevention and Control C5- Core Competencies in Management of Medications	30	60

Table 4: Showing module 1 and 2 having competencies of health care communication and advanced nursing core competencies.

Details on Major and Specific Competency Skill Sets included are:				
Module No.	Core Competencies	Specific competencies	Hours Allotment	
			Theory	Practical
III	Core competencies in technology-based teaching & learning	C1- Core Competencies in Planning & designing teaching and learning strategies (class room/ online) settings C2- Core Competencies in ICT (including eHealth, mHealth, Clinical Simulation gaming, etc.) C3- Core Competencies in clinical reasoning among diverse learners with unique learning needs C4- Core Competencies in individualized experiential learning	30	60
IV	Core competencies of monitoring and evaluation	C1- Core Competencies in cognitive domain assessment - formative and summative assessment in relation to learning outcomes C2- Core Competencies in affective domain assessment – feedback by students and peers to improve role effectiveness C3- Core Competencies in psychomotor domain assessment – OSCEs, OSBEs & CQIs C4- Core Competencies in nursing curricula evaluation and revision framework	30	60
4	4	18 specific competencies	100	200

Table 5: Showing module 3 and 4 having competencies of technology based teaching & learning methods and monitoring and evaluation respectively.

Method of Evaluation and examination details							
Formative Assessment – Theory		Formative assessment – Practical's		Summative assessment			
				Theory	Marks	Practical	Marks
Written Assignment	25 Marks	Case Study	25 Marks	Objective type	25	Skill Demonstration	25
Seminar/ Symposium	25 Marks	Nursing rounds Anecdotal reports /	25 Marks	2 marks	25	Case Presentation	25
IA- test	25 Marks	OSCE	25 Marks	5 marks	25	Nursing Care path/ algorithm	25
Total	75	-	75	-	75		75
Final Internal Assessment Theory & Practical – 25 each (25%)				Final summative assessment of theory & practical- shall be 75%			
Total IA- 25 +75= 100 for theory & practical							

Table 6: Showing details of method of evaluation and examination involving formative and summative assessment.

Discussion

There are several obstacles facing nursing education today, such as rising health care costs, declining public support, and a lack of public acceptance of the need for more sophisticated and specialized training given the demands of contemporary nursing care. The parties involved in health care must work to address these problems and go past them. One such move in that regard is CBNE, which attempts to guarantee a thorough examination and improvements in the nursing education sector.^[13]

The public's expectations and the nursing profession's scope of practice have changed throughout time, with a focus on developing nursing skills and providing high-quality patient care.

Barriers to nursing abilities can be broadly classified into three categories. Institutional, situational, and dispositional obstacles are the three types of barriers. Situational impediments might include things like problems with the physical and social surroundings. Institutional obstacles include things like a dearth of institutional incentives, procedural issues, and a lack of appealing or pertinent academic programmes provided. Psychosocial and attitudinal obstacles are examples of dispositional barriers. All things considered, the obstacles include lack of knowledge regarding CBNE and programme scheduling and convenience.^[14]

A self-administered questionnaire and focus group talks were among the study's instruments. The self-administered surveys were built around the following themes: clinical biological science, ethics and accountability, general clinical abilities, lifelong learning, caring, and critical thinking and reasoning. A seven-point Likert scale is used to assess each item on the original scale, indicating the level of skill attained. For each question, there were seven possible responses: 1 for not at all, 2 for never, 3 for occasionally, 4 for often, 5 for frequently, 6 for almost always, and 7 for always.

One of the noteworthy results of the FGT was the agreement that chances for professional development and leadership training including younger nursing faculty members, as well as employer assistance for career growth, were highly recommended. Nurses defined healthy work environments as those that made investments in chances for ongoing professional development to guarantee practice growth and deliver the best possible patient care.

Examining the viability of senior nursing faculties as a "reservoir of skills and experience" that may be efficiently exploited for the further growth of CBNE was one of the main topics covered at the FGD. You can access the expertise of senior nursing faculty members who are in the middle to end of their careers for research, skill development, and mentoring. The need of properly recognizing the "seniority of nursing faculties" was emphasized, since doing so will greatly aid organizational efforts to lower attrition rates and enhance the pool of potential employees. Similar opinions were also voiced in a Price et al. investigation.

According to our analysis, CBNE is a positive trend that benefits all parties involved in the healthcare industry, including employers, medical and paramedical workers, and patients. To get long-term benefits, the CBNE programme should be implemented with sincerity and appropriate time and staff allocated, along with frequent feedback analysis.^[15]

Conclusion

We conclude that for successful implementation of CBNE better communication skills with emphasis on inter personal relationships along with good Academic performance using better learning resources is extremely essential.

References

1. Beecroft, P.C.; Dorey, F.; Wenten, M. Turnover intention in new graduate nurses: A multivariate analysis. *J. Adv. Nurs.* 2008, 62, 41–52.
2. Bowles, C.E.; Candela, L.E. First job experiences of recent RN graduates: Improving the work environment. *J. Nurs. Adm.* 2005, 35, 130–137.
3. Boychuk Duchscher, J.E.; Cowin, L. Multigenerational nurses in the workplace. *J. Nurs. Adm.* 2004, 34, 493–501.
4. Meyer Bratt, M.; Felzer, H.M. Predictors of new graduate nurses' organizational commitment during a nurse residency program. *J. Nurses Staff Dev.* 2012, 28, 108–119.
5. Laschinger, H.K.S. Job and career satisfaction and turnover intentions of newly graduated nurses. *J. Nurs. Manag.* 2012, 20, 472–484.
6. Day, R.; Field, P.; Campbell, I.; Reutter, L. Students' evolving beliefs about nursing: From entry to graduation in a four-year baccalaureate programme. *Nurse Educ. Today* 2005, 25, 636–643.
7. Kelly, J.; Ahern, K. Preparing nurses for practice: A phenomenological study of the new graduate in Australia. *J. Clin. Nurs.* 2009, 18, 910–918.
8. McKenna, L.; McCall, L.; Wray, N. Clinical placements and nursing students' career planning: A qualitative exploration. *Int. J. Nurs. Pract.* 2010, 16, 176–182.
9. Kovner, C.T.; Brewer, C.S.; Fairchild, S.; Poornima, S.; Kim, H.; Djukic, M. Newly licensed RNs' characteristics, work attitudes, and intentions to work. *Am. J. Nurs.* 2007, 107, 58–70.
10. McDonald, A.W.; Ward-Smith, P. A review of evidence-based strategies to retain graduate nurses in the profession. *J. Nurses Staff Dev.* 2012, 28, E16–E20.

11. Park, M.; Jones, C.B. A retention strategy for newly graduated nurses: An integrative review of orientation programs. *J. Nurses Staff Dev.* 2010, 26, 142–149.
12. Armstrong-Stassen, M.; Cameron, S.; Rajacich, D.; Freeman, M. Do nursing managers understand how to retain seasoned nurses? Perceptions of nurse managers and direct care nurses of valued human resource practices. *Nurs. Econ.* 2014, 32, 211.
13. Armstrong-Stassen, M. Human resource management strategies and the retention of older RNs. *Nurs. Leadersh.* 2005, 18, 50–64.
14. McGillis Hall, L.; Lalonde, M.; Dales, L.; Peterson, J.; Cripps, L. Strategies for retaining midcareer nurses. *J. Nurs. Adm.* 2011, 41, 531–537.
15. Weidner, A.; Graham, C.; Smith, J.; Aitken, J.; Odell, J. Alberta: Evaluation of nursing retention and recruitment programs. *Nurs. Leadersh.* 2012, 25, 130–147.